

Surface smoothing and periodic microstructuring of additively manufactured scalmalloy® by sequential continuous-wave polishing and direct laser interference patterning

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ABSTRACT

Laser Powder Bed Fusion is gaining industrial prominence due to its ability to create complex parts with reduced material waste. Scalmalloy® stands out as a possible replacement for titanium, offering high strength and thermal conductivity while maintaining low component weight. Nevertheless, parts produced by this method normally exhibit high surface roughness, characterized by partially melted particles and surface irregularities. In addition, low surface roughness is also a prerequisite for the further fabrication of well-defined microstructures that can enhance surface functions based on mimicking natural examples. This work combines surface smoothing by continuous-wave laser re-melting with the fabrication of periodic textures using Direct Laser Interference Patterning to tailor surface topography. Initial laser polishing trials achieve a substantial reduction of as-built Ra roughness from approximately (Ra) ~14 μm to 1–2 μm but generated subsurface pores. The porosity is mitigated by adjusting laser power and feed rate. The polished samples are subsequently microstructured by DLIP using a picosecond pulsed laser, producing structure depths up to 3.0 μm with a homogeneity of approximately 82%. Finally, the performance of the combined process is analyzed in terms of energy consumption and target surface parameters to improve process sustainability.

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM) has become an important technology in aerospace design due to its ability to fabricate complex, lightweight, and near-net-shape components while reducing material waste [1]. Among the available AM techniques, Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) is widely used for the production of metallic parts requiring high design freedom under optimized process conditions [2,3]. High dimensional accuracy can be achieved in LPBF, although it may be affected by thermal distortion, material shrinkage, and process parameter variability. At the same time, the qualification of AM components for aerospace service remains challenging due to process variability, defect sensitivity, economic factors, and size constraints, particularly for

fatigue-critical structural parts. These capabilities and constraints motivate research aimed at improving surface condition control and post-processing efficiency, which are directly linked to performance and manufacturability [4,5]. In this context, high-strength and lightweight aluminum alloys have gained significant interest as candidate materials for additively manufactured components. However, processing of these alloys by LPBF present specific processing challenges due to inherent material properties, including low laser energy absorption, high thermal conductivity, pronounced oxidation tendency, and strong sensitivity to process parameters [6–8].

These processing challenges have motivated the development of aluminum alloys designed explicitly for LPBF. One such alloy is Scalmalloy®, a high-performance Al–Mg–Sc–Zr system engineered to provide

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high specific strength and a microstructure suitable during AM [6,9]. The alloy, originally developed by Airbus SAS for aerospace applications, exploits the unique rapid solidification conditions in LPBF to achieve adequate mechanical properties through controlled precipitation of nanoscale Al₃(Sc,Zr) particles [10,11]. Despite these advantages, additively manufactured components of this alloy often exhibit relatively poor as-built surface quality. The resulting surface roughness, typically ranging from 10 to 25 μm in LPBF, is influenced by multiple factors including layer thickness, powder particle size distribution, laser parameters, and part orientation [12–18]. This relatively high initial surface roughness can significantly reduce fatigue and functional performances, making post processing necessary [19–21].

Traditional post-processing methods for reducing surface roughness in LPBF produced parts include generally mechanical machining (like turning, milling or manual grinding and polishing) [22] and chemical etching [23]. However, each of these post-processing routes is associated with specific drawbacks. For example, mechanical methods require a tool or abrasive to be in contact with the part, generating geometric restrictions and material wastage. Chemical methods present environmental constraints due to the generation of harmful byproducts [16,24]. Alternatively, laser-based polishing has been researched as a suitable non-contact post-processing technique for additive manufactured components, offering the ability to process complex geometries, without introducing additional consumables.

In laser-based polishing, controlled remelting of the upper surface layer is induced, and surface tension forces subsequently redistribute molten material from protrusions into depressions, thereby reducing roughness [25,26]. For aluminum alloys processed by laser powder bed fusion, several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of laser polishing in improving the surface quality of AlSi10Mg. For instance, El Hassanin et al. showed a substantial decrease in the surface roughness of laser-polished parts using CO₂ laser radiation from 19.4 to 3.3 μm [27]. In other work, Zhou et al. achieved roughness reductions up to ~70% (from 12.5 to 3.7 μm) by in-situ polishing LPBF parts utilizing the same laser source used for sample fabrication [28]. Furthermore, Hofele et al. reported that laser polishing using also a cw-laser could achieve surface roughness reduction up to 97.5% for LPBF AlSi10Mg parts depending on the initial roughness of the part, highlighting its potential for enhancing surface quality in additive manufacturing [16].

Despite its remarkable efficiency in reducing surface roughness, laser polishing faces several challenges that require further investigation. One significant issue that can affect the outcome of the process is the formation of sub-surface pores due to the trapping of dissolved gases because of rapid solidification. This phenomenon is strongly dependent on the processing conditions, which necessitate precise control of the laser parameters to minimize defects formation [29,30]. In addition, although laser polishing has been extensively studied for other aluminum alloys, the number of studies addressing its effects on Scalmalloy® remains limited. For instance, Kuisat et al. used a nanosecond-pulsed laser to reduce the surface roughness of Scalmalloy® from 19.6 to 6.8 μm , representing reductions up to 65% [31]. Since the laser polishing process was performed using nanosecond pulses (200 ns), partial material ablation occurred. These findings indicate that alternative laser polishing strategies for Scalmalloy® should be investigated.

Laser radiation can also be used to impart new functionalities to a surface and thus improve the performance of AM-produced components [32,33]. This can be achieved for instance, by creating periodic surface structures having feature sizes in the nanometer and/or micrometer ranges. In the context of surface texturing, laser micro-fabrication methods — such as Direct Laser Writing (DLW), where a focused laser beam moves relative to the workpiece to create desired surface structures through controlled local melting or ablation — can provide a flexible and fast solution for creating new functionalities by tailoring sample topography [34]. Nonetheless, the lateral resolution of the surface features produced by this technique is generally limited to the diameter of the laser beam at the focal position (typically 15–45 μm). To

overcome this limit, Direct Laser Interference Patterning (DLIP) offers a promising alternative by enabling the creation of high-resolution periodic structures with feature sizes even below 1 μm , enhancing surface functionalities significantly. DLIP is based on the interference of multiple coherent laser beams to fabricate periodic surface structures by locally ablating or melting the material at interference maxima positions [35,36]. Changing the geometrical arrangement of the sub-laser beams as well as phase and polarization, several interference patterns can be generated [37]. In particular, two-beam interference configurations have been widely studied for the fabrication of line-like periodic structures using laser sources spanning pulse durations from the nanosecond to the femtosecond regime. This approach has been shown to impart new surface functionalities, such as friction reduction and wettability modification, in a single processing step without the use of external etching agents [38–40].

In recent years, the application of DLIP to aluminum-based alloys, particularly those produced by additive manufacturing, has received growing attention. For instance, Kuisat et al. successfully used a two-beam DLIP configuration to produce line-like structures and simultaneously reducing the initial surface roughness in a similar LPBF aluminum alloy. The produced patterns permitted to increase the static water contact angle from 16.3° to 131.4° [41]. In the case of Scalmalloy®, promising results regarding the functionalization of surfaces using also a two-beam DLIP configuration have been reported by the same author. The freezing time of water droplets in contact with the laser-treated Scalmalloy® surface was increased by 127%, indicating an enhanced resistance to ice formation [42].

When applied to additively manufactured components, the effectiveness of direct laser interference patterning and other laser-based microstructuring techniques is strongly influenced by the initial surface condition. In particular, the relatively high as-built roughness typical of additive manufacturing can hinder the formation of homogeneous periodic surface structures [42]. Consequently, the optimization of the initial surface quality through appropriate post-processing, such as laser polishing, becomes a critical prerequisite for fully exploiting the capabilities of DLIP. Despite this, the combined application of laser-based polishing and laser interference patterning for surface functionalization has been only sparsely investigated and has largely focused on materials other than Scalmalloy® [43–45]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the use of laser polishing followed by DLIP employing a ps-pulsed laser source, together with its optimization toward energy-efficient fabrication of highly homogeneous structures, has not yet been reported for additively manufactured Scalmalloy® parts. Therefore, this work investigates the generation of a surface roughness suitable for DLIP processing on LPBF Scalmalloy® by laser polishing, while minimizing polishing-induced subsurface porosity and determining an energy-efficient process window for the sequential process chain.

The main goal of this study is to develop a sustainable two-step laser-based process for roughness reduction and micro-structure fabrication to enhance the surface quality and microstructuring capability of additively manufactured Scalmalloy® components. Following coupon fabrication, samples undergo post-processing through laser polishing until roughness is reduced to a level suitable for DLIP processing. Once this threshold is fulfilled, DLIP is used to fabricate periodic line-like patterns on top of the polished surface. The obtained surface characteristics are then evaluated using a systematic approach to determine the optimum process window, focusing on reaching a balance between energy consumption and surface quality. In addition, a subset of the coupons is subjected to sandblasting prior to laser polishing to assess its influence on the required laser processing parameters. Application-specific validation (e.g., fatigue testing and qualification thresholds for pores and textures) is outside the scope of this manuscript. Accordingly, we restrict conclusions to surface/topography outcomes and process windows. However, the insights gained on surface optimization will serve as foreground for the sustainable manufacturing of functional

complex shaped parts in future works.

2. Materials and methods

Scalmalloy® (Al-Mg-Sc-Zr) coupons were manufactured by Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) using a Renishaw AM500E (Renishaw, UK) equipped with a 500 W Ytterbium fiber laser. The manufacturing process was performed under an argon atmosphere, maintaining an oxygen content below 500 ppm inside a $250 \times 250 \times 350 \text{ mm}^3$ chamber on a $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ heated platform using TOYAL Europe powder and $30 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ layers. The volumetric energy density was maintained at 85.6 J mm^{-3} by using a laser power of 370 W, a scan speed of 1600 mm/s, and a hatch distance of $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. In addition, a stripe scan strategy with a 5 mm stripe width and a 67° layer-to-layer rotation was applied. Post-build heat treatment consisted of furnace ramp from room temperature to $325 \pm 5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. After reaching the plateau, this temperature was then stabilized for 15 min and maintained to anneal the samples for 4 h [29]. Finally, the produced parts were cooled down at a rate of $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Two initial surface conditions were prepared: as-built (post-heat-treat) and sandblasted to a uniform baseline roughness. The sandblasting process was performed in a SBF 8 \times 6 machine (Abrasive y Maquinarias S.A., Spain) using industrial glass beads with a particle size distribution between 40 and $70 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ at a pressure of 8 bar.

Afterward, Laser polishing was performed using a 3D SYLAS SLEEK 1000 system (Fig. 1a). The system includes a 1 kW continuous wave diode laser source with a central wavelength of 980 nm (LDM 1000–30, Laserline, Germany), having a focusing optics resulting in a spot diameter of approximately 0.9 mm. Laser polishing was performed in an argon-flushed enclosure keeping oxygen levels below 500 ppm. Argon was injected into the chamber at 5 l/min and the O_2 concentration was measured with a SGM7 sensor (Ziross, Germany). During the polishing processes, the output power of the laser was varied between 430 W and 820 W, while the studied scan rates ranged from 25 mm/s to 550 mm/s. After polishing, the samples were processed using Direct Laser Interference Patterning (DLIP). The coupled laser source was a solid-state InnoSlab PX200–3–GF laser (Edgewave, Germany) delivering pulses with a pulse width of 12 ps at a wavelength of 1064 nm. The outgoing laser beam was then guided by mirrors and fed into an DLIP-ELIPSYS® optical head (Surfunction GmbH, Germany, EU patent EP3990211B1). The optical head splits the incoming beam by means of a diffractive optical element into two sub-beams. These beams are posteriorly shaped and overlapped at the working position to generate a line-like interference pattern with a spatial period of $6.0 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ over an elongated elliptical spot ($\sim 875 \times 75 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$). The general schematic of the DLIP system is depicted in Fig. 1b. For processing the samples, laser fluences of 1.2 and 2.0 J cm^{-2} were applied at repetition rates of 10 and 20 kHz. Pulse-to-pulse overlaps were varied in steps from 75.00 to 99.95% (discrete steps being 75%, 80%, 85%, 90%, 92.5%, 95%, 99%, 99.5%, 99.9%, 99.95%) in order to investigate the effect of different cumulated laser fluence on structure morphology. These parameter ranges correspond to typical operating conditions reported for DLIP processing of metallic

materials and were selected to cover regimes from moderate to very high pulse overlap. Processing parameters for both LP and DLIP are condensed in Table 1.

Initial and post-polishing surface roughness was measured using a mechanical roughness tester (PCE-RT2300, PCE instruments, UK) using a cut off wavelength of 0.8 mm and a Gaussian filter. For roughness evaluation, five measurements were performed at spatially separated locations within the processed area. Measurement positions were selected to avoid sample boundaries as well as scan lead-in and lead-out regions. For evaluation of the subsurface microstructure and porosity, cross-section of the samples was performed using a mounting press (REMET IPA 30, EVOLUTION, Remet, Italy) and polishing equipment (REMET LS2, Remet, Italy). Then, images were taken using optical microscopy (BX41MLED, SC30 camera, Olympus, Japan). Pore area fraction was quantified from a subset of metallographic cross-section micrographs (three per selected polishing condition) using a Python/OpenCV workflow. A filled sample mask was first extracted to isolate the metallic region and exclude the mounting resin. To reduce interface artefacts, the sample mask was eroded by a user-defined boundary exclusion width. Pores were segmented using Gaussian smoothing followed by inverse Otsu thresholding within the final analysis ROI. The total pore area fraction was computed as the summed contour areas divided by the final ROI area.

For characterizing the resulting DLIP topographies, a surface profiler was used (Sensofar S Neox 3D, Sensofar Metrology, Spain). Specifically, a $50\times$ white light interferometry (WLI) objective with a lateral and vertical resolutions of $0.50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and 0.1 nm was used for capturing topographical data. For each processed area, an area $1.93 \times 0.50 \text{ mm}^2$ was measured. Average structure-depth was then obtained by processing the measured areas using SensoMap 7 (Sensofar Metrology, Spain). Furthermore, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were obtained using a Sigma 300 Gemini (Zeiss, Germany) at an acceleration voltage of 3 kV.

Using an adaptation of the Gini coefficient method, DLIP homogeneity was computed from WLI topographies using $300 \times 300 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$ windows centered on each track. For this purpose, the topography images were divided into square unit cells with a side length equal to the spatial period. Then, within each cell, relevant topographic features were quantified and the Gini coefficient was calculated for all cells. The parameters used for this evaluation included the structural height of the DLIP features, as well as skewness (Ssk) and kurtosis (Sks). Skewness (Ssk) is used to describe the asymmetry of the height distribution with respect to the mean surface plane, whereas kurtosis (Sks) characterizes the sharpness of peaks within that distribution. Both parameters together provide a comprehensive description of the surface topography in terms of shape, roughness, and texture symmetry. Finally, the geometrical mean of the extracted parameters was calculated to obtain an overall value for structure homogeneity. A detailed description of this method can be found in previous work by Soldera et al. [46]

Finally, a multi-objective cost function was used to evaluate the effectiveness of the dual laser-based fabrication process. The characteristic values measured from the resulting topographies, together with

Fig. 1. Schematics of (a) laser polishing system and (b) Direct Laser Interference Patterning setup using two interfering laser beams for surface microstructuring.

Table 1
General process parameters for Laser Polishing and DLIP.

Parameter	Laser polishing	DLIP
Pulse duration	CW	12 ps
Central wavelength	980 nm	1064 nm
Spot size	$0.9 \text{ }\mu\text{m} \times 0.9 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$	$875 \text{ }\mu\text{m} \times 75 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$
Process atmosphere	Argon filled chamber	Ambient air
Oxygen level	< 500 ppm	–
Laser fluence	–	1.2, 2.0 J/cm^2
Repetition rate	–	10 kHz, 20 kHz
Pulse to pulse overlap	–	75%–99.95%
Laser power	430 W – 820 W	–
Scan rate	25 mm/s – 550 mm/s	–

the utilized laser energy for both the polishing and interference patterning steps, were incorporated in the function to rank the used parameter sets and identify energy-efficient operating windows. A detailed description of the methodology is available in previous work by the authors [45].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Laser polishing treatment

In this section, the laser polishing results are presented in two stages, including an initial parameter screening to evaluate surface roughness and subsurface porosity over a broad cumulative fluence range (Section 3.1.1), followed by a focused optimization at reduced fluence levels (Section 3.1.2).

3.1.1. Laser polishing parameter screening

In the first stage, the LP process (see Fig. 1a) was implemented on the Scalmalloy® coupons. Exemplary SEM images presented in Fig. 2 show the initial state of the material surface as well as its condition after the LP treatment. Fig. 2a shows the as-built condition of the additively manufactured Scalmalloy®. The surface is characterized by partially melted powder particles, surface defects and a heterogeneous distribution of surface features, which are typical in surfaces produced by LPBF [47].

Differently, after the LP treatment, almost all the particles have been melted, and a significant reduction of the above-mentioned defects can be observed, as shown in Fig. 2c. In addition, the laser-polished sample shows a smoother surface, confirming the effectiveness of the LP treatment. The observed surface smoothing results from the shallow remelting induced by the continuous-wave laser during the polishing process. Under these conditions, a transient molten layer is formed, and surface tension forces drive the redistribution of material from surface asperities into adjacent valleys, leading to a reduction in roughness as reported by several authors [28,48].

The effect of laser cumulated fluence from the laser polishing treatment on the surface roughness (R_a) for the treated Scalmalloy® samples was systematically investigated, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The cumulated

fluence was increased by changing both the laser power and scanning speed up to 150.0 J/mm^2 . The shaded band in Fig. 3a represents the initial roughness of the as-built (AsB) condition ($R_a = \sim 13 \mu\text{m}$) of laser powder bed fusion parts. This roughness is consistent with previously reported values for additively manufactured Scalmalloy® [31]. As it can be seen, in the figure, an important reduction in surface roughness was achieved with increasing the cumulated laser fluence for power levels above 430 W.

For coupons subjected to sandblasting prior to laser polishing (Fig. 3b), a similar trend was observed. However, in this case, surface roughness reduction was achieved at lower cumulative fluences when a laser power of 430 W was applied. For instance, while the as-built condition exhibited a R_a roughness of approximately $8.9 \mu\text{m}$ at a cumulative fluence of 43.0 J/mm^2 , the sandblasted coupons reached R_a values as low as $1.9 \mu\text{m}$ under the same cumulated fluence conditions. The enhanced polishing efficiency observed for sandblasted samples at lower laser power can be attributed to the removal of partially fused powder particles and the reduction of extreme surface asperities prior to polishing. As a result, a continuous and stable molten surface layer can be formed at lower energy input, whereas the as-built condition requires higher power to fully melt residual particles and enable effective surface smoothing. Nevertheless, since comparable surface roughness values were obtained after laser polishing for both surface conditions, this indicates that sandblasting primarily influences the early stages of roughness reduction but does not affect the surface quality achievable after polishing [16].

However, while topographical defects seem to be mitigated by the LP treatment, cross-sectional investigations from the laser treated coupons (at 150 J/mm^2 , with a laser power of 750 W at a scanning speed of 25 mm/s) reveal the presence of pores beneath the polished surface at depths of approximately $150 \mu\text{m}$ (see Fig. 2d). Such subsurface pores can negatively influence mechanical performance, including tensile strength, ductility, and strain-to-failure, and are particularly relevant for fatigue behavior, as they act as stress concentrators and potential crack initiation sites [49–53]. Accordingly, the high-fluence condition shown here is treated as a boundary case to delineate process limits rather than an application relevant process window.

In addition, their size and morphology suggest an origin related to

Fig. 2. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) images of (a) as-built (c) laser-polished Scalmalloy® coupons and corresponding cross-sectional investigations (optical microscope images) for the (b) as-built and (d) laser polished coupons. The laser-polished coupon from images (c) and (d) was treated at a laser power of 750 W and a scanning speed of 25 mm/s resulting in a cumulated fluence of 150.0 J/mm^2 .

Fig. 3. Resulting surface roughness values (Ra) as a function of the applied cumulative laser fluence during laser polishing for (a) as-built and (b) sandblasted Scalmalloy® coupons. The shaded regions in the figures indicate the initial surface roughness (including standard deviation) prior to laser polishing.

gas entrapment caused by the rapid vaporization of alloying elements present in Scalmalloy®. In particular, magnesium is an alloying element present in Scalmalloy®, and its vaporization is considered a primary contributor to gas- and keyhole-related porosity during laser polishing due to its low boiling point and high vapor pressure under laser irradiation. Similar observations have been widely reported in the literature for other laser-based processes, including additive manufacturing and laser welding, across multiple alloy systems [54–57].

Consequently, additional cross-sectional analyses were performed on selected laser-polished coupons exhibiting the surface roughness values reported in Fig. 3. The corresponding optical microscopy images are presented in Fig. 4. The analyzed samples were processed using different combinations of laser power and scanning speed while maintaining comparable cumulative laser fluence levels. In this context, image pairs

(a, d), (b, e), and (c, f) correspond to three representative processing conditions with cumulative fluences of 86.0, 43.0, and 21.5 J/mm², respectively.

Despite identical cumulative fluence values, cross-sectional analyses revealed clear differences in subsurface pore morphology, as shown in Fig. 4. For the highest fluence condition (86.0 J/mm²), the samples processed at lower scanning speed (25 mm/s, see Fig. 4a) exhibited a higher number of large, nearly spherical pores, whereas the corresponding sample processed at higher scanning speed (50 mm/s, see Fig. 4d) showed a finer and more uniformly distributed porosity. The spherical morphology of the pores suggests they are driven by gas expansion, as mentioned before. In Al-Mg-Sc alloys like Scalmalloy, this is typically attributed to the selective vaporization of Magnesium (which has a low boiling point of ~1090 °C) and the precipitation of dissolved

Fig. 4. Optical micrographs corresponding to cross-sections of the laser polished coupons using different laser parameters. Coupons (a,d), (b,e) and (c,f) were processed maintaining the same laser cumulated fluence of 86.0, 43.0 and 21.5 J/cm², respectively.

hydrogen. The high laser energy density heats the melt pool well above the boiling point of Mg, causing it to transition to vapor and form stable bubbles that are trapped upon rapid solidification. Scandium, possessing a much higher boiling point (~ 2836 °C), remains stable in the melt and does not contribute to vapor-induced porosity. Furthermore, in this high-energy configuration, the substantial heat input creates a voluminous melt pool with a prolonged lifetime, allowing pre-existing microporosity from the AM substrate to coalesce and expand due to thermal heating, while providing sufficient time for hydrogen and Mg precipitation [58].

In contrast, processing at higher speeds (50 mm/s, Fig. 4d) increases the local solidification rate, affecting pore morphology, since the time available for pore nucleation and growth is shorter, leading to a decrease in both pore size and volume fraction [59]. Consequently, while the porosity generation mechanism remains the same, the reduced interaction time and rapid solidification arrest bubble expansion early, resulting in a distribution of finer pores rather than the large voids. This behavior was also observed for the samples treated with at lower cumulated laser fluences (43.0, and 21.5 J/mm²), and different scanning speeds. However, due to the lower heat input, the size and number of pores was reduced (Fig. 4b, c, e, and f).

To quantitatively support these observations, image analysis was performed on the cross-sectional micrographs to determine the total pore area fraction, which is summarized in Fig. 5. The results show that lower cumulative fluence levels (<40 J/mm²) are associated with a limited amount of subsurface porosity, whereas increasing the used fluence leads to a pronounced increase in total pore area (up to $\sim 4\%$). The figure also indicates that polishing at higher laser power and increased scan speed reduces porosity. These findings indicate that effective surface smoothing can be achieved at relatively low cumulative fluences while minimizing subsurface defect formation. Therefore, reduced polishing fluence levels were selected for the subsequent surface structuring experiments.

3.1.2. Laser polishing optimization at reduced cumulative fluence

To address the subsurface porosity observed at higher energy inputs, an additional series of laser polishing experiments was performed using an adjusted set of processing parameters. The objective was to achieve effective surface smoothing while minimizing pore formation. Based on

the results described in Section 3.1.1, the cumulative fluence was identified as one of the most relevant factors governing pore development. Accordingly, the cumulative fluence was maintained below a threshold of 21.0 J/mm², requiring the use of increased laser power combined with higher scanning speeds.

Fig. 6 summarizes the results obtained using the optimized laser polishing parameters, showing the resulting surface roughness (Ra) as a function of the applied cumulative fluence. As in the initial parameter screening, the data are grouped according to the initial surface condition, namely (a) as-built and (b) sandblasted prior to polishing. In each plot, the shaded regions represent the initial surface roughness of the corresponding condition.

Fig. 6a shows that, for the as-built sample group, surface roughness reduction remains limited at cumulative fluence levels below 10.0 J/mm², with the exception of the condition employing a laser power of 820 W and a scanning speed of 500 mm/s. At higher cumulative fluence values, a pronounced decrease in Ra is observed, followed by saturation at approximately 2 μm .

For the sandblasted coupons, lower surface roughness values are obtained at cumulative fluence levels below 10.0 J/mm², with Ra values approaching approximately 2 μm . This behavior indicates that surface pre-treatment enhances the efficiency of laser polishing at reduced energy input. However, comparable roughness levels are ultimately achieved for the as-built samples at higher cumulative fluences. Among the investigated conditions, the combination of a laser power of 820 W and a scanning speed of 250 mm/s resulted in the lowest Ra values, namely 1.59 μm for the as-built condition and 1.53 μm for the sandblasted condition. This corresponds to a roughness reduction of 88 and 85%, for the as-built and sandblasted conditions, respectively.

Following laser polishing, cross-sectional investigations of the coupons exhibiting the lowest Ra values (mentioned above) were prepared and examined by optical microscopy. As shown in Fig. 6c and d, a substantial reduction in pore presence was observed for both as-built and sandblasted samples, with pores being hardly detectable in the latter case. These results indicate that the optimized polishing parameters effectively improve surface quality while suppressing subsurface porosity. Consequently, samples processed under these polishing conditions were selected for the subsequent picosecond DLIP treatment discussed in Section 3.2.

Fig. 5. Pore area fraction (%) as a function of cumulated laser fluence during laser polishing.

Fig. 6. Surface roughness (Ra) as a function of the applied cumulative laser fluence during laser polishing for (a) as-built and (b) sandblasted Scalmalloy® coupons. The dotted lines indicate the initial surface roughness prior to laser polishing. OM cross section images of coupons polished using laser power 820 W and a scan rate of 250 mm/s: (c) as-built and (d) sandblasted.

3.2. Direct laser interference patterning treatment

The DLIP process using picosecond laser pulses was implemented to fabricate line-like periodic structures over the laser polished Scalmalloy® coupons with a spatial period of 6.0 μm, as described in the experimental section. The surfaces (both AsB and SB conditions) were irradiated at different pulse-to-pulse overlaps as well as laser fluences resulting in very different surface patterns. Exemplary images of the treated surfaces are shown in Fig. 7. Fig. 7a and d show the typically obtained topography when using relatively low overlaps (80%). As can be seen, for both AsB and SB conditions, the produced line-like structures have a shallow structure depth (0.6 μm).

Increasing the overlap up to 95% produced deeper structures, reaching a structure depth of approximately 3.0 μm for the as-built condition, when applying a laser fluence of 2.0 J/cm² (see Fig. 7b) which approaches an aspect ratio (AR) of 0.5 (the AR is defined as the quotient between the structure depth and the spatial period). These depths are typical for metals irradiated at similar conditions [39,60]. In addition, for the above-mentioned processing parameters, the formation of laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS) was observed [45]. Based on their orientation perpendicular to the laser beam polarization

and their spatial period of approximately ~900–1000 nm, these features can be classified as low-spatial-frequency LIPSS (LSFL), whose characteristic dimensions are on the order of the applied laser wavelength (1064 nm). It should be noted that the occurrence of LIPSS was limited to a narrow processing window, which is consistent with previous reports on aluminum alloys [61]. For the sandblasted condition, partial deterioration of the irradiated surface was observed (Fig. 7e).

For samples processed with pulse-to-pulse overlaps exceeding 99%, the line-like structures were severely damaged due to the excessively high applied energy density for both, as-built and sandblasted conditions. Under these conditions, the resulting surface topography consisted of irregular peaks and valleys lacking long-range order (see Fig. 7c and f). These conditions are included to identify the upper boundary of stable periodic structuring; they are not proposed as suitable windows for functional surfaces.

Following, the influence of the applied process parameters for the DLIP treatment on the structure depth was further analyzed. Fig. 8 shows the measured average structure depth of the DLIP line-like structures as function of the pulse-to-pulse overlap (OV%), for samples both as-built (Fig. 8a) and sandblasted (Fig. 8c). The results show that the structure depth increased when increasing the pulse-to-pulse overlap

Fig. 7. SEM images of Line-like periodic patterns produced using ps-DLIP at 2.0 J/cm^2 of laser fluence and a repetition rate of 10 kHz in Scalmalloy®. The used pulse-to-pulse overlaps were: (a, d) 80%, (b, e) 95% and (c, f) 99.95%. (a, b, c) As-Built; (d, e, f) Sandblasted.

for all used fluences (1.2 and 2.0 J/cm^2) and repetition rates (10 and 20 kHz) until an overlap of 95%. In addition, it can be seen that the error bars, that describe variations in the structure depth in the analyzed area, also were lower. For samples processed with pulse-to-pulse overlaps exceeding 99%, the line-like structures were severely damaged due to the excessively high applied energy density for both, as-built and sandblasted conditions. Under these conditions, the resulting surface topography consisted of irregular peaks and valleys lacking long-range order (see Fig. 7c and f), which is typical in metallic surfaces when using DLIP in combination with ps pulses [45]. Therefore, data points for structures processed at overlaps higher than 99% are not plotted in Fig. 8.

The results presented in Fig. 8 further indicate that the applied repetition rates (10 and 20 kHz) do not have a significant influence on the reached structure depths. Instead, the increase in cumulative fluence is identified as the primary factor governing structure growth, as already reported for several metals and metallic alloys [45,62,63]. This behavior can be attributed to the use of picosecond laser pulses at these repetition rates, for which heat accumulation effects are negligible [64]. Besides, similar structure depths were obtained for both as-built and sandblasted samples, indicating that the ablation efficiency remains largely independent of the surface condition prior to laser polishing.

The homogeneity of the resulting surface topographies was quantified using the Gini coefficient, as described in the Experimental section, following the method proposed by Soldara et al. [46], Fig. 8b summarizes the homogeneity values obtained for the as-built samples, while Fig. 8d presents the corresponding results for the structures fabricated on sandblasted coupons. As shown in the diagrams, the calculated homogeneity remains relatively constant over the investigated overlap

range, with values around 80% for both as-built and sandblasted coupons. This behavior suggests that the achievable homogeneity is constrained by residual surface irregularities introduced during laser polishing. As shown in Fig. 2c, localized voids and topographical non-uniformities remain present after polishing, which limits further increases in texture homogeneity beyond $\sim 80\%$.

These findings have shown that reducing the surface roughness of LPBF Scalmalloy® by laser polishing is necessary to enable controlled DLIP structuring. The large surface asperities typical of as-built AM surfaces can disturb the interference-induced energy distribution and thus limit the quality of the resulting periodic structures [42].

3.3. Cost function analysis

A multi-objective cost function analysis was performed to evaluate the combined laser polishing and Direct Laser Interference Patterning process applied to additively manufactured Scalmalloy®. Because the sequential route is intended for surface treatment of extended areas and potentially complex geometries, energy input represents an important practical constraint that must be balanced with surface-quality targets. The aim of this analysis is therefore to identify processing conditions that balance topography metrics relevant for periodic microstructuring (depth, aspect ratio, homogeneity) with the cumulative energy required for polishing and DLIP. This evaluation approach was previously developed and applied to laser-based surface functionalization of additively manufactured Ti-6Al-4V components [45]. Sandblasting was included as an industrially relevant pre-treatment condition to assess how the initial surface state influences the parameter window of the sequential polishing and DLIP process.

Fig. 8. Structure depth (a,c) and homogeneity (b,d) of the line-like produced patterns by ps-DLIP as function of the pulse-to-pulse OV on Sandblasted (a,b) and As-Built (c,d) coupons. For the DLIP treatment, the used laser wavelength was 1064 nm, and the pulse duration 12 ps.

The cost function used in this work is given in Eq. (1):

$$Cf = w_{AR} \frac{AR_{target}}{k_{AR} + AR} + w_{F_{cum}} \frac{F_{cum}}{k_{F_{cum}} + F_{cum}} + w_{F_{pcum}} \frac{F_{pcum}}{k_{F_{pcum}} + F_{pcum}} + w_H \frac{|H - H_t|}{k_H + |H - H_t|} + w_{pol} \frac{Ra_{target}}{k_{pol} + Ra} \quad (1)$$

Each contribution to the cost function follows the general form of $C_i = w_i \cdot x_i / (k_i + x_i)$, which ensures that the parameter x_i grows the cost in a smooth manner, saturating at a maximum value given by the weight (w_i). Based on previous application of this approach [45], the selected target parameters considered in the present study include the Aspect Ratio (AR) of the DLIP structures, the cumulated fluence (F_{cum}) used for the DLIP treatment, the cumulated fluence for the polishing process (F_{pcum}), structure homogeneity (H) of the final DLIP features and the surface roughness parameter R_a obtained after the polishing treatment. The weighting coefficients and normalization constants used for the cost function evaluation are summarized in Table 1. The weighting coefficients in Table 2 are not universal constants. They encode the relative priority assigned here to achieving stable periodic microstructures while limiting cumulative fluence, and they follow the previously demonstrated structure of the method [45]. The selected weights and normalization constants were chosen to keep each contribution bounded and comparable in magnitude, avoiding dominance by units or scale.

Fig. 9 shows the resulting cost function values for the experiments

performed in this study. The optimum processing conditions that minimize the cost function for both as-built and sandblasted coupons (black

triangles) are listed in Table 3. WLI images of the structures that yielded both the lowest and highest cost are highlighted also included the figure. Namely, the WLI images shown in Fig. 9b and Fig. 9c, corresponding to

Table 2
Initial values of cost function coefficients.

Coefficient	Value
w_{AR}	20
AR_{target}	0.5
k_{AR}	0.25
$w_{F_{cum}}$	25
$k_{F_{cum}}$	20
$w_{F_{pcum}}$	15
$k_{F_{pcum}}$	10
w_H	25
H_t	1
k_H	1
w_{pol}	15
k_{pol}	1
$Ra_{target} [\mu m]$	0.5

Fig. 9. (a) Calculated cost function for the different process parameters (n test) used in this study, for both As-built and Sandblasted coupons. WLI images of the structures that yielded the lowest cost for As-built (b) sandblasted (c) and highest overall cost (d).

Table 3
Process parameters needed to reach the lowest cost values for both AsB and SB coupons.

Initial surface finish	Cost value [a. u.]	AR	Structure depth [μm]	OV [%]	Cumulated Fluence DLIP [J/cm ²]	Polishing Power [W]	Homogeneity [a. u.]	Initial roughness [μm]
AsB	45.88	0.52	3.1	95%	40	820	0.81	13.65
SB	45.83	0.52	3.1	95%	40	820	0.82	10.13

the as-built and sandblasted conditions, respectively. In Fig. 9d, the surface that yielded the highest cost is depicted. In this case, it can be seen that the surface presents severe over melting and randomized peaks. These exemplary topography images serve to illustrate the capability of the employed equation to identify a suitable process window. Furthermore, the lowest cost function values for both as-built and sandblasted coupons were very similar (45.88 and 45.83 for as-built and sandblasted coupons, respectively, see Table 3).

It should be noted that the energy consumption associated with the sandblasting step was not included in the cost function evaluation. Consequently, when the additional intermediate treatment is considered, sandblasted samples would be expected to result in a higher overall process cost.

4. Conclusions

This study investigated a sequential two-step laser-based route for the surface treatment of additively manufactured Scalmalloy®. Continuous-wave laser polishing was applied to reduce the LPBF as-built roughness, and DLIP using a picosecond pulsed laser was subsequently used to generate periodic line-like microstructures. The objective of this study was to obtain a surface condition suitable for DLIP by laser polishing without introducing subsurface defects and to identify a processing window with limited energy input.

Laser polishing enabled substantial roughness reduction in Scalmalloy®, with Ra decreasing from ~13–14 μm (as-built) to ~1.5–2.0 μm depending on cumulative fluence and scan strategy. However, cross-

sectional analyses revealed that high cumulative fluence can lead to subsurface porosity beneath the produced smooth surface, indicating that roughness alone is not sufficient as polishing-quality criterion. By applying lower cumulative fluences (<21.0 J/mm²) combined with higher scanning speeds (>200 mm/s), a surface roughness (Ra) of ~1.5 μm was achieved while limiting subsurface porosity compared with high-fluence conditions.

Using these polished surfaces, DLIP method permitted to produce 6.0 μm periodic line-like textures with structure depths up to ~3 μm and surface homogeneities of ~80%. Structure depth increased with pulse-to-pulse overlap up to ~95%. However, overlaps exceeding ~99% led to severe deterioration of the pattern quality for both initial surface conditions.

Finally, a multi-objective cost function was used to evaluate the sequential process conditions by combining surface-quality targets and energy consumption. Similar optimal process parameter combinations were obtained for both as-built and sandblasted starting conditions (cost values ~45.9; overlap ~95%; depth ~3.1 μm; homogeneity ~0.81–0.82).

While specific functional applications were beyond the scope of this work, the proposed cost-function approach can be used in future studies to optimize surface functionality and component performance. Application-specific validation, including fatigue testing and qualification criteria for pores and surface textures, remains to be addressed in future studies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ignacio Tabares: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ugo Andral:** Methodology, Investigation. **Mario Escudero:** Methodology, Investigation. **Antonio Perinán:** Methodology, Investigation. **Bogdan Voisiat:** Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Sonia P. Brühl:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Andrés Fabián Lasagni:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Given his/her/their role as Editor of the Journal Surface and Coatings Technology, Sonia P. Brühl had no involvement in the peer review of this article and had no access to information regarding its peer review. Full responsibility for the editorial process for this article was delegated to another journal editor. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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